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◆	Students' Achievement in Relation to School Climate in Rural High and Normal Effective Elementary Schools	60-62
	<i>Narendra Kumar Moharana, Prof. (Dr.) Sura Prasad Pati</i>	
◆	Fascination for Women in the Life and Works of Hemingway	63-64
	<i>Dr. Rakesh Kumar Singh</i>	
◆	Archaeological significance of the Sidhi region in Madhya Pradesh	65-69
	<i>Sunil Kumar Singh</i>	
◆	Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana : Progress and its Benefits	70-71
	<i>Dr. Satyendra Kumar Dubey & Dr. Panna Lal Dwivedi</i>	
◆	State and Market in Economies of BRICS Countries During 2003-15	72-74
	<i>Ravish Kumar Shukla</i>	
◆	Factors Affecting Employability of Graduates of Faculty of Social Sciences, BHU Other than General Employability Skills	75-79
	<i>Pradeep Kumar Singh</i>	
◆	Role of Total Quality Management in Software Technology & Industry	80-82
	<i>Dr. Garima Agarwal</i>	
◆	A Challenging Role of SIDBI for Development of Small Scale Industries in India	83-85
	<i>Dr. Shiv Shankar</i>	
◆	Cruelty in Dowry Death : A Socio - Legal study	86-88
	<i>Simsim Verma</i>	
◆	Secularism in India	89-92
	<i>Subham Chaorasiya, Ankita Pandey</i>	
◆	Role of I.T. in Advancement of Education	93-96
	<i>Dr. Shiv Shanker Shukla</i>	
◆	Tourism Entrepreneurship : Thrust Areas for Action	97-99
	<i>Rahul Singh</i>	
◆	Contextualising India's Identity Politics through Dalit and Backward Classes	100-103
	<i>Suraiya Nazee</i>	
◆	Before Dupleix: The Early History of French Company in India	104-108
	<i>Brijesh Kumar Shukla</i>	

Before Dupleix: The Early History of French Company in India

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Towards the end of 16th century we come across the first European appearance at the court of Indian emperor, Portuguese missionaries at the court of Akbar. But the first official contact came in during the reign of Jahangir when Sir Thomas row, ambassador the then English king, appeared at Mughal court to seek permission of trade. This event marked the inflow of Europeans of various nationalities, Portuguese, Dutch, French, Swiss, Den and of course the British, on Indian soil. As our study is limited to the French presence in India, we shall be tracing on French lineage in detail.

At the time when the Asian wars were being decided by the superior cavalry, western European militaries were engaged in development of tactical manoeuvres, drill patterns for their infantry. By the 17th Century European gunners had made their place as artillerymen in the Indian armies.¹ They were sought after by every army because of their usefulness in besieging forts.²

This time also coincided with the foundation and growth of the French and English trading enterprises. With the beginning of disintegration of Mughal Empire, these then traders of various nationalities got engaged into conflict for maximum profit by ensuring monopolies in various commodities and regions. In their respective regions they recruited locals into their own armies. French were the pioneers in this in Carnatic and were soon followed by the British in Madras.³ Select officers were sent to train and command the infantry and artillery sections of the armies of neighbouring Indian rulers.

The English were more successful as a trading-conquering company than the French, but paradoxically French adventurers were more prominent in the armies of Indian kingdoms.⁴ The process finally resulted in the establishment of English authority for two centuries. In this establishment of British Empire most fierce challenge to the English came from their continental arch rivals the French.

Establishment of French company : Before discussing about the formation of the French East India Company, it would be crucial to understand the economic and political milieu of the France from where the Company had originated. Between sixteenth and eighteenth centuries, western European nations (Netherland, Britain, France etc.) underwent fundamental shifts in their political, social and economic structures. All these European powers adopted a variety of mercantilist policies, designed to enrich both state and local merchant class.

In the course of several years of development, France had gradually evolved a kind of transformation from medieval anarchy and papal domination into a strongly centralised nation. For instance, the era of Louis XIV aimed at the establishment of a new and strong France in the eyes of Europe in her Political, social and economic front.⁵ The territorial enhancement and commercial activities were to be carried out through a policy of expansion.

Other countries who were doing trade towards Asia were selling Asian commodities in France, which has also become the cause of drain of wealth from to other nations.⁶ Besides this, French were also loosing the various such opportunities that could have helped them in various ways for the improvement of their economy, naval expansion, and stronger position in Europe.

During this period in France the formulation of a national commercial policy was largely the work of Colbert, who for twenty two years from 1661 to 1683 was the Finance minister to Louis XIV. In the process many companies were established.⁷ Madagascar was planned to be colonised to develop as a midway resting place.⁸ This plan resulted in large expenditure from the royal treasury. In spite of the Kings backing and a lot of propaganda to motivate the French people to settle in the island, projects proved a failure.⁹

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Colbert had great faith in the chartered company as a means of promoting trade and he was responsible for the establishment of numerous companies which he used for the acquisition and development of colonies and as his chief weapon against the commerce of other nations.¹⁰ The creation of chartered companies with monopoly rights was only one though perhaps the most important, feature of the mercantilist policy of exclusion. This principle of excluding foreigners from all intercourse with the colonial domain was known as the “Colonial Pact”.¹¹

It was Colbert who provided the chief impetus to the foundation of the “*Compagnie des Indes Orientales*” in the Year 1664. From 1664 the French imperial policy changed under the influence of Colbert’s grand design. When the company was established in the year 1664, the French were not altogether unaware of the mechanics of trading with the East.¹²

But, it had difficulty gaining the financial support of French merchants, and Colbert is thought to have pressured many of them to join.¹³ He pushed François Charpentier to publish an attractive announcement about the benefits of getting into the company, asking why the French should trade in gold, pepper, cinnamon, and cotton. Further Charpentier proved that the French paid 12% more for Indian goods obtained through the Dutch than what they should be paying if they “fetched them themselves” and that they consumed at least one third of “what was brought out of India”¹⁴ Louis XIV wrote to 119 towns, ordering merchants to gather and discuss subscribing to the company, but many refused. King also conceded to Company an advance of three million francs.¹⁵

Further Louis XIV was pleased to issue the Edict which was to form the basic constitution of the company on 27th August 1664. To state a few privileges in brief, “all were invited to invest in the “*Compagnie des Indes Orientales*” including the foreigners.¹⁶ By 1668 the French monarch was the biggest shareholder, and the company was to stay under his authority.¹⁷

Colbert after colonising Madagascar decided to direct his efforts towards India.

French Company Comes to India : French travellers such as Françoise Bernier, Jean-Baptiste Tavernier and François Le Gouz de la Boullaye had made voyages to the Indes in 17th century and their accounts of travel had already made French elite and society familiar with India. Bernier was engaged as a physician at Mughal court during early years of Aurangzeb and later on with Prince Dara.¹⁸

Le Gouz, who later became the first ambassador of King Louis XIV to the Mughal emperor Aurangzeb, had travelled India between 1646 to 1649 AD. On his return to Paris he published observations and accounts of his voyage in 1653.¹⁹ Thus he was an obvious choice for being ambassador of France to Mughal court. In 1664 he again started voyage to India to obtain permission for the establishment of factory of French company. In the letter Louise asked for permission to setup factories and protection for the French nationals.²⁰ Aurangzeb granted a *farman* to French embassy in September 1666. The French company was formally permitted to open up trade with Indian merchants and erect a factory at Swali, a small rural port outside Surat.²¹

In France it was now decided to despatch the first convoy to India. It started in 1667 and arrived at Surat in early 1668. In this convoy François Caron was entrusted with the second embassy to Delhi. Caron had been the director of the Dutch company and when he retired, Colbert invited him to join the French company as director. On arrival at Surat Caron set about constructing the factory.

The French Company faced two major issues in establishing itself in India. First was the difficulty of negotiating with local kings and princes for special trading rights and privileges. Second was the opposition from the other European companies like the Dutch and the English, who had already established their position.²²

Bernier advised Caron to follow the policy of “mediocrement”, that is to speak moderately, of the power and greatness of King of France.²³ But Caron had the different solution. In order to solve these difficulties, Caron persuaded the King and the company to send out a strong naval fleet to India.²⁴ Louis XIV and Colbert sent a strong fleet under M. De La Haye with the aim to “show the Indian princes and merchants a sample of the power and the prowess of the king of France”.²⁵ Their idea was to impress the natives and to coax and bully them to offer commercial privileges to the French company.

Caron succeeded getting a *farman* from the great Mughal granting the same trading rights as the Dutch and the English.²⁶ In the meantime Caron proposed some plans for the company’s

further extension to new areas. On December 5, 1669, French Company's agent Marcara obtained a *farman* from the King of Golkunda permitting the French Company to trade in Kings dominion without duty and to establish a loge at Masulipattnam.²⁷

Foundation and Growth of Pondicherry : Definitely Francois Martin was the most notable figure among the early French men in India. He was born in 1634 to a grocery merchant and was provided good education. With his poor income he was forced to join French East India Company and sailed to Indes in 1665. After several years of service in Madagascar, Surat and Masulipattanam, in 1674 Martin was sent to tiny settlement of Pondicherry which the French company had acquired in southern Coromandel coast.

Soon after his arrival, Martin developed friendly relations with natives and local governor. Martin had lent some money to the Sher Khan which could not repay. In return Martin sought permission from Sher Khan Lodi to erect such buildings as would be necessary to secure his people and their property from desultory attacks.²⁸ Martin constructed slender defences. Houses soon came up within this area and a small village for the local population who worked for the factory soon grew up within the walls.²⁹ From 1672 until 1693 when it was taken by the Dutch, the French, under the command of François Martin, managed to set up a factory in this locality, to build a fort, magazines, stores, to attract craftsmen and succeeded, in spite of the difficulties, in making of this small village a fairly large and prosperous settlement. The detailed history of this expansion is well known, as it is described almost day by day by François Martin himself in his fascinating *Mémoires*.³⁰

In May 1677, Sher Khan Lodi was defeated by the invading Marathas.³¹ Shivaji expected martin to remain neutral in ensuing conflict. Soon, French were rewarded for adhering to the advice.³² A Maratha *farman* dated 15 July 1677, permitted the French to build warehouses not only in Pondicherry but also in any other village or town for the purpose of storing merchandise. More dwellings and store houses came up. In 1689, Sambha Ji, son of Shivaji, permitted Martin to make use of the defences that he had erected, to build a regular fort.³³ This policy, which the French adopted, of making native alliance the means by which they might ultimately gain their ends, was above all things unaggressive in character; and so it remained until the time of Dupleix.

When Pondicherry was made the seat of the Director General with supreme authority over the French factories in any part of the India, Francois Martin became the first president of the Superior Council and Director General of the French affairs in India.³⁴ In 1703, he purchased the village of Kalapet from governor Dawood Khan, the representative of Aurangzeb in Carnatic. This he did for the aim of getting timber from the forests close the place for the development of homes in Pondicherry. At the time of Martin's death, on December 30, 1706, Pondicherry was a prosperous French settlement, with 700 Europeans and thirty,000 Indians. Martin had reworked Pondicherry from a small fishing village into an active port city that served as the principal outpost of French mercantilism in the east.

Every fresh addition to the power of the French under Martin, Lenoir, and Dumas, was made without striking a blow, and, in the case of the two first, without making an enemy. Throughout the time that M. Benoit Alexander Dumas remained governor-general of the French settlements in India, he maintained an in depth friendly relationship with Dost Ali, the governor of the Carnatic, and continuing to increase this friendly relationship to his family when his death. By means that of this friendly relationship he obtained from the Emperor of Delhi, through the mediation of Dost Ali, the permission to mint coins at Pondicherry associate item of no little importance within the growth of French commerce in India.³⁵

It is safe to argue that resistance of Dumas may be said to have created a prestige, without the aid of which the glorious career of the French subsequently would scarcely have been possible. The respect and fame, which the French had now picked up, was, besides, of no normal kind. They had taken a huge risk against a most considerable adversary, not from any impulse, but rather essentially in light of the fact that they had resolved to remain by their companions.

Henceforth the French occupy a distinctly higher status, and are by all recognized as by no means the least of the powers of India. Thanks, accompanied by the most valuable presents, came to the French from all the great native powers. The Emperor of Delhi himself through Nizam conferred on the Governor of Pondicherry and his successors the rank and title of *nawab*, and the high dignity

of the command of 4500 horses.³⁶ The original *farman* was translated and sent to the directors of the company in January 1742. This document makes it incontestable that Dumas was the first French *Nawab* of Pondicherry.³⁷ Dumas, after resignation, was replaced by Joseph François Dupleix, the then Governor of Chandernagore, Dumas had laid down the base of French power in India - now the opportunity rested in the hands of Dupleix to raise the high-rise buildings.

Conclusion : The story so far told can be concluded by saying that French rose to political prominence very quickly. They were the last European power to enter into India but were the first to mingle in the affairs of the native powers. They were first who could make out that there exist a vacuum in the diplomatic, political and military arena of India.

It was Francois Martin who developed very cordial relations with the natives. It was Governor Dumas who “hired out” French troops in return of territorial concession. This, then, innovative use of trained army started the concept of hiring the others army.³⁸ Thus, I will conclude that the before Dupleix also the French had acquired considerable hold among the Indian powers.

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